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Brand equity and consumer buying behavior: Determinants of intentions to visit-tourism destinations in Cavite, Philippines

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Abstract

By highlighting the four dimensions that constitute brand equity, and the four factors that influence the selection and decisions of consumers, this research aimed to assist tourist destination owners and managers in creating a brand and knowing their target market and their preferences when it comes to spending their money. The descriptive correlational and comparative methods were employed on 339 BSTM students during the first semester of SY 2022-2023. This study revealed that majority of the guests were female, young, with a family earning above minimum wage in a month, and living in the urban areas of Cavite. Perceived quality and Psychological factors came out to be the most dominant factors they considered in visiting tourist destinations. There is no significant difference in the perceived brand equity when grouped according to their demographic profile. There is no significant difference in the respondents' buying behavior when grouped according to their demographic profile. There is a significant relationship between perceived brand equity and buying behavior. This study recommends that a step-by-step approach should be used, from identifying who the brand is to emphasizing its points of uniqueness and user profile. Customers may therefore positively assess and develop a link that will lead to an enduring and unbreakable bond, which shapes and impacts their purchasing decision. The analysis of this study concludes that Tourism Destinations in Cavite with higher levels of brand equity would generate higher levels of customer visits. Also, consumer buying behavior was associated with more willingness to visit a destination.

Keywords: Brand Equity; Consumer Buying Behavior; Cvsu College Students; Tourism Destinations

1. Introduction

For many nations, tourism is a large fraction of the economy. For policymakers to effectively create vacation destinations, tour packages, and the industry as a whole, it is crucial to understand the elements that affect tourists' choice of destination. Tourism industries continue to grow as crucial factors in economic growth. There are a lot of arguments on the determinants influencing the choice of tourism destinations and attractions. Some of these are its location, infrastructure, money, amenities, facilities, security, and recommendations from reputable sources. Aside from these, the brand equity and buying behavior of the consumers is attracting a lot of attention to industries. The idea of building a brand and focusing on brand equity within the context of a tourism destination is being used as a gauge by many governments and tourism service providers. Although many different dimensions and paradigms make up brand equity, numerous studies have identified some explicit or implicit characteristics of a city or nation that, as a tourist destination, support a particular brand. A destination naturally becomes its brand, supported by a variety of additional features. For example, due to current challenges for the tourism sector, opportunities arise to encourage innovation, drive new business models, explore new niches/markets, open up new destinations, and move to more sustainable and resilient tourism development models (OECD, 2020).

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As regards buying behavior this is one major aspect of tourism that draws a lot of attention. This would focus on why a tourist chooses a destination and what are the predominant reasons that influence someone's decision in traveling. Sec. Christina Garcia Frasco (2022) mentioned that through Philippine President Ferdinand Romualdez Marcos Jr. (Bong Bong) directive to light up the country's tourism promotions, and the recent easing of mask mandates, the Philippines is indeed opening doors to the world. Cavite province is to be included in particular in the Heritage Tourism Campaign. The province is replete with history, culture, and cuisine. Cavite has a significant role in the country's colonial past, especially in the nation's fight for independence. It is one of the first few provinces to cradle the Philippine revolution. Indeed a concrete example of a promising and historical tourist destination. Cavite is a coastal province situated in the south of Manila. Its location near the airport is one of its assets as a tourism destination for local and foreign visitors. The geography of the province varies differently, the lowland and coastal areas in the north and west, and the upland areas in the south and east. In the lowland areas, travelers usually visit historical sites and seafood specialties. While, in the upland areas, the cool breeze of Tagaytay City is what usually attracts visitors. But the province has so much more to offer aside from its already popular attractions. Some tourist spots are often overlooked and underestimated.

Due to the distinctive characteristics of the service industry and the dominance of experience and credence traits, it is frequently claimed that marketing in the service industry is extremely challenging. Due to consumers' difficulty in evaluating services before purchasing, one particular effect is that perceived risk is typically higher in service selection decisions (Parasuraman et al., 1985; Laing et al., 2002; Mitchell, 1999). In this circumstance, the brand might be crucial as a risk reliever, giving customers more assurance in their buying decisions and fostering trust. (Erdem and Swait, 1998).

In essence, the brand tells customers what kind of service they can expect, which helps alleviate some of the issues related to experience and credibility issues (De Chernatony and McDonald, 1998). Because the brand is a source of information, it can act as a risk-reduction tool as well as a tool for differentiation and can facilitate consumer choice by establishing distinctiveness (Gabbott and Hogg, 1998). As a result, the brand has become a crucial factor in influencing consumer decision-making buying behavior in the service industry (Turley and Moore, 1995).

In a sense, tourism destinations must understand how to utilize brand equity in attracting tourist visits. Growth in the tourism and hospitality industry markets has stimulated competition between businesses. This study has allowed a closer look at the intention to visit the Cavite province as a tourist destination based on brand equity and consumer buying behavior among students of Cavite State University (CvSU). The study also focuses on understanding visitor purchasing patterns, which is crucial information for all tourism-related businesses in promoting their products and services. It is any method of gathering a person's actions, attitudes, and choices regarding the selection, purchase, and consumption of products and services, as well as their reactions thereafter. Understanding consumer behavior is essential to the success of business organizations. Consumer behavior can be defined as the study of how, when, what, and why people make purchases. Furthermore, a variety of factors—including cultural, social, personal, and even psychological ones—influence customers' buying behaviors. This is a portion of human comportment and by studying previous buying behavior, business managers would be able to evaluate how consumers make decisions (Bathan, 2017).

By highlighting the four dimensions that constitute brand equity, and the four factors that influence the selection and decisions of consumers, this research could assist tourist destination owners and managers in creating a brand and knowing their target market about their preferences when it comes to spending their money. Thus, this study.

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to emphasize in CvSU college students' intentions to visit tourism destinations in Cavite based on brand equity and consumer buying behavior. Specifically, this aimed to 1) identify the demographic profile of the CvSU college students in terms of age, sex, place of Residence (rural or urban), and monthly Family income; 2) determine the brand equity of tourism destinations in Cavite as perceived by the CvSU college students in terms of brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality; 3) determine the CvSU college students' buying behavior in tourism destinations of Cavite in terms of cultural, social, personal and psychological factors; 4) assess if there is a significant difference in the perceived brand equity when grouped according to the demographic profile of CvSU college students; 5) analyze if there is a significant difference in the CvSU college students' buying behavior when grouped according to their demographic profile; and 6) analyze if there is a significant relationship between perceived brand equity and the buying behavior of CvSU college students.

1.1. Hypothesis

H1: There is no significant difference in the perceived brand equity when grouped according to the demographic profile of CvSU college students.

H2: There is no significant difference in the CvSU college students' buying behavior when grouped according to their demographic profile.

H3: There is no significant relationship between perceived brand equity and the buying behavior of CvSU college students.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Research Design

To test the hypothesis and to answer the questions concerning brand equity and the buying behavior of students to tourism destinations in Cavite, descriptive correlational and comparative methods were used in the study.

It is descriptive because it entails description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the demographic profile of the CvSU college students. Their age, sex, place of residence, and family income were described. The brand equity of tourism destinations in Cavite as perceived by the CvSU college students was described based on brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality. More so, the CvSU college students' buying behavior in terms of cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors was recorded, described, and analyzed. It is correlational because this study attempted to correlate the perceived brand equity and the buying behavior of CvSU college students. It is comparative because it attempted to distinguish the differences between the perceived brand equity when grouped according to the demographic profile of CvSU college students, and CvSU college students' buying behavior when grouped according to their demographic profile.

2.2. Research Instrument

A research instrument in the form of a questionnaire was administered to the students. The responses were tabulated, recorded, and analyzed. There are three parts to the instrument. Part I determined the demographic profile of the CvSU college students. Basic information about the respondents like age, sex, place of residence, and family income was recorded and tabulated. Part II of the Questionnaire dealt with the brand equity of tourism destinations in Cavite as perceived by the CvSU college students: brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality were likewise determined. Part III of the questionnaire focused on the buying behavior of CvSU college students in terms of cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors. The part II of the questionnaire was adapted from the research study of Erenkol, H. A. D., et. al., (2010); Sun, B.J., (1996); and Tran, V.T., et.al., (2019). Similarly, part III of the questionnaire was adapted from the research study of Bathan, A. C. L, et. Al (2017). These measurements used a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4 to present strongly disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree.

2.3. Sampling Technique

Stratified random sampling will be used in the study. It is a type of sampling method in which the total population is divided into smaller groups or strata to complete the sampling process. The strata are formed based on some common characteristics in the population data. After dividing the population into strata, the researcher randomly selects the sample proportionally. In this study, proportionate random sampling will be used. Each stratum would have the same sampling fraction. Each of the three groups will be equally represented by 50 percent. Therefore the second year will cover 135 randomly selected students, 78 for the third year, and 126 for the fourth year with a total sample of 339 randomly selected students out of 677 total population.

2.4. Participants

The participants of the study were 339 BSTM students, second to fourth-year level and currently enrolled during the first semester of the school year 2022-2023 at the Home Economics, Vocational, and Technical Education Department, College of Education Cavite State University-Main Campus, Indang, Cavite.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure

The study was conducted via an online survey (using Google Forms) that was sent directly to the participants using Facebook Messenger. The data collection was undertaken in October 2022.

2.6. Statistical Procedures

Data were analyzed by using statistical tools such as Frequency, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, Kruskal-Wallis H, Mann-Whitney U Test, and Spearman's Correlation. These statistical tools gave meaning to the bulk of data and provided interpretation to the study.

Frequency count was used to determine the number of observations that fall under a given category like age, sex, place of residence, and family income. Percentage was used to determine the percentage of total observations falling under a given category. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the brand equity of tourism destinations in Cavite as perceived by the CvSU college students in terms of brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality; and the buying behavior of CvSU college students in terms of cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Kruskal-Wallis H and Mann-Whitney U Test were used to determine the degree of difference between the demographic profile of CvSU college students with perceived brand equity and buying behavior. Specifically, Kruskal-Wallis H was used for the age, year level, place of residence, and monthly income profile because these have three or more groups or categorical variables. For the sex profile, the Mann-Whitney U Test was employed because it only has 2 groups or categorical variables (either male or female). Spearman's Correlation was used to determine a significant relationship between the perceived brand equity and the buying behavior of CvSU college students. The Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient (Spearman's correlation, for short) is a nonparametric measure of the strength and direction of association that exists between two variables measured on at least an ordinal scale.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Demographic profile of the cvsu college students

Table 1 Distribution of student participants according to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 years old and below	14	4
19 to 20 years old	161	48
21 to 22 years old	136	40
23 years old and above	28	8
Total	339	100

Age: The table shows that out of 339 participants, 161 (48%) of them were from 19 to 20 years old, 136 (40%) belonged to the 21 to 22 age group, 28 (8%) of them were 23 years old and above and the remaining 14 participants (4%) belonged to 18 years old and below age group. Participants of this study are mostly in their second-year level which justifies the age of the majority. It further implies that participants belonged to a young age group.

The findings affirm that of Fishman (2017) who claimed that 63 percent of Americans believe the average college student is 20 years old.

Table 2 Distribution of student participants according to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	56	16
Female	283	84
Total	339	100

Sex: Table 2 shows that the majority of the participants 283 (84%) are female and 56 (16%) are male. There are more females than males which implies that the BS Tourism Management program is more attractive to females. This further

shows that tourism students are female-dominated and this could be explained by the recent statistics that the Philippines is a female-dominated country in terms of sex.

Similarly, Owen (2003) revealed an interesting finding that female students make greater use of university services and value higher education more than male students.

Table 3 Distribution of student participants according to Place of Residence

Place of Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Alfonso	12	3.5
Amadeo	6	1.8
Bacoor City	10	2.9
Carmona	3	0.9
Cavite City	4	1.2
Dasmariñas City	46	13.6
General Emilio Aguinaldo	1	0.3
General Mariano Alvarez	10	2.9
General Trias City	66	19.6
Imus City	18	5.3
Indang	36	10.6
Kawit	2	0.6
Magallanes	3	0.9
Maragondon	1	0.3
Mendez	6	1.8
Naic	19	5.6
Noveleta	3	0.9
Rosario	2	0.6
Silang	11	3.2
Tagaytay City	8	2.4
Tanza	31	9.1
Ternate	2	0.6
Trece Martires City	39	11.5
Total	339	100.0

Place of Residence: Cavite has 7 cities namely Bacoor City, Cavite City, Dasmariñas City, General Trias City, Imus City, Tagaytay City, and Trece Martires City; and 16 municipalities namely Alfonso, Amadeo, Carmona, Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo, Gen. Mariano Alvarez, Indang, Kawit, Magallanes, Maragondon, Mendez, Naic, Noveleta, Rosario, Silang, Tanza, and Ternate. As shown in table 3, the majority of the students reside in General Trias City, Dasmariñas City, and Trece Martires City which comprised 66 (19.6%), 46 (13.6%), and 39 (11.5%) respectively. This was followed by 36 (10.6%) from Indang, 31 (9.1%) from Tanza, 19 (5.6%) from Naic, 18 (5.3%) from Imus City, 12 (3.5%) from Alfonso, and 11 (3.2%) from Silang. 10 (2.9%) students live in Bacoor City and Gen. Mariano Alvarez, respectively. Followed by eight (2.4%) students who live in Tagaytay City. Six (1.8%) call Amadeo and Mendez home. Four (1.2%) are Cavite City residents. Three (.9%) live in Carmona, Magallanes and Noveleta. Two (.6%) reside in Kawit, Rosario, and Ternate. Gen.

Emilio Aguinaldo and Maragondon both have one (.3%) student. The findings indicate that participants were mostly living in the urban parts of Cavite.

The above finding on the place of residence aligns with the data gathered by Florida (2019) which stated that across the American nation, college graduates are overwhelmingly concentrated in urban areas. Almost 90 percent of college grads live in urban counties, with more than 60 percent of them in large metros with over one million people. Just a bit more than one in ten college graduates reside in rural communities. But this is largely because urban areas simply have a larger population than rural areas.

Table 4 Distribution of student participants according to Monthly Family Income

Monthly Family Income	Frequency	Percentage
Less than Php 10,000	121	35.7
Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	126	37.2
Php 20,001 to Php 30,000	67	19.8
Php 30,001 and above	25	7.4
Total	339	100.0

Monthly Family Income: Findings revealed that the majority of the students have Php 10,001 to Php 20,000 (37.2%) monthly family income. This was followed by 121 (35.7%) students with less than Php 10,000 monthly family income. 67 (19.8%) students have a monthly family income of Php 20,001 to Php 30,000 and the remaining 25 (7.4%) students have a monthly family income of Php 30,001 and above. These findings show that the majority of the students are from lower-income families.

National Statistics Office (2008) supported the above findings and discussed that the annual average family income in Cavite is Php 196,401.00 or Php 16,366.75 per month. Contrary to the findings, the Provincial Government of Cavite Offices and Departments (2020) stated that the average minimum wage rate in Cavite is Php 357.50 for the non-agriculture industry or Php 8,580.00 per month.

3.2. Brand equity of tourism destinations in cavite

Table 5 Brand Loyalty as perceived by student participants

Brand Loyalty	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Tourist Destinations in Cavite would be my first choice when travelling	3.12	0.706	Agree
2. I would advise other people to visit tourist destinations in Cavite that I've been through	3.55	0.595	Strongly Agree
3. I would continue to visit tourist destinations in Cavite even if they increase prices	2.97	0.729	Agree
4. I can distinguish Cavite tourist destinations among other destinations outside the province	3.17	0.708	Agree
5. Brand loyalty will always have a positive impact on intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination	3.51	0.636	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.26		Strongly Agree

Findings indicated that 'I would advise other people to visit tourist destinations in Cavite that I've been through', got the highest mean of 3.51; while 'I would continue to visit tourist destinations in Cavite even if they increase prices' got the lowest mean of 2.97. Generally, students strongly agree that brand loyalty leads to intentions to visit tourism destinations in Cavite with an overall mean of 3.26. These findings imply that loyal visitors will persuade others to travel

to the tourism destinations they have already experienced. Brand loyalty plays a crucial part in marketing and competition because competitors may be inhibited from investing resources to obtain happy and loyal customers already.

This finding was strengthened by the study of Kothari and Maindargi (2019) who examined the effect of brand loyalty on each dimension of consumer buying behavior related to retail trade in Solapur City. They found that in the retail industry, as per the grocery trade is concerned, consumers know the brands available in markets and do not show a willingness to switch their brands.

Table 6 Brand Awareness as perceived by student participants

Brand Awareness	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Tourist destinations in Cavite have good name and reputation	3.46	0.571	Strongly Agree
2. Tourist destinations in Cavite are very famous	3.29	0.653	Strongly Agree
3. When I think about traveling, a tourist destination in Cavite comes to mind immediately	2.90	0.831	Agree
4. Tourist destinations in Cavite have recallable slogans and campaigns	3.04	0.735	Agree
5. Brand awareness is the most effective way that increases the intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination	3.54	0.566	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.25		Strongly Agree

Findings indicated that 'Brand awareness is the most effective way that increases the intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination', got the highest mean of 3.54; while 'When I think about traveling, a tourist destination in Cavite comes to mind immediately' got the lowest mean of 2.90. Generally, students strongly agree that brand awareness leads to intentions to visit tourism destinations in Cavite with an overall mean of 3.25. These findings imply that travelers consider well-known tourist destinations when they travel. Awareness affects the choice by influencing which brands are chosen and considered by others. Before being on the purchasing list, the brand must first join the consideration set.

The findings conform to the study of Masika (2013) who found that brand awareness had the most powerful influence on consumers' purchase decisions. Brand awareness is an element that plays a vital role in a consumer's choice of brand. It is also supported by Lin and Chang (2003) who examined the importance of brand awareness in consumers' decision-making process and found that brand awareness was a primary factor in consumer buying behavior.

Table 7 Brand Associations as perceived by student participants

Brand Associations	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I prefer tourist destinations in Cavite over other competitors	2.86	0.736	Agree
2. Some characteristics and features of the tourist destinations in Cavite come to my mind quickly	3.09	0.714	Agree
3. I can distinguish the tourist destination brand through the shapes, colours, and symbols associated with the mark	3.07	0.722	Agree
4. Tourist destinations in Cavite are fashionable and modern	3.18	0.689	Agree

5. Brand association motivates the intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination	3.44	0.614	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.13		Agree

Findings indicated that 'Brand association motivates the intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination', got the highest mean of 3.44; while 'I prefer tourist destinations in Cavite over other competitors' got the lowest mean of 2.86. Generally, students agree that brand associations lead to intentions to visit tourism destinations in Cavite with an overall mean of 3.13. These findings imply that when people travel, they take into account whatever memories or impressions they may have of the destinations' brands.

This finding is similar to the study of Ashraf, Sulehri, and Abbas (2018) who examined the impact of the brand association dimensions on consumer responses. Their results revealed a positive relationship between the brand association dimensions on consumer buying behavior. The brand association functions are the guarantee, social identification, personal identification, and status that positively impact the recommendation, extension of purchase from the same brand, and price premium.

Table 8 Perceived Quality as perceived by student participants

Perceived Quality	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Tourist destinations in Cavite provide tourism offerings of consistent quality	3.31	0.581	Strongly Agree
2. Tourist destinations in Cavite provide quality experiences	3.38	0.570	Strongly Agree
3. I can expect superior performance from the tourist destinations in Cavite	3.25	0.639	Strongly Agree
4. I feel safe in my travels with tourist destinations in Cavite	3.35	0.629	Strongly Agree
5. Perceived quality is the driving force for the intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination	3.46	0.571	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35		Strongly Agree

Findings indicated that 'Perceived quality is the driving force for the intentions of guests to visit a tourist destination', got the highest mean of 3.46; while 'I can expect superior performance from the tourist destinations in Cavite' got the lowest mean of 3.25. Generally, students strongly agree that perceived quality leads to intentions to visit tourism destinations in Cavite with an overall mean of 3.35. These findings imply that before making a purchase, travelers do take into account a product or service's general quality or superiority compared to alternatives/ competitors for the intended use.

In tourism and hospitality, destination brand quality is a core dimension of brand equity when applied to a tourism destination (Boo et al., 2009; Pike et al., 2010; Bianchi and Pike, 2011; Myagmarsuren and Chen, 2011, Yuwo et al., 2013; Tran et al., 2017). According to Konecnik and Gartner (2007), destination-perceived quality can be defined as the perceptions of tourists toward a destination about its capability to fulfill their travel-related expectations and demands. Similarly, Pike et al. (2010) consider destination-perceived quality as tourists' opinions related to the quality of a destination's infrastructure, hospitality services, and amenities, such as accommodation.

3.3. CVSU college students' buying behavior

Table 9 shows the Cultural Factors Affecting the CvSU college students' Buying Behavior with an overall mean of 3.54 rated as Strongly Agree. Findings indicated that 'makes creative design dedicated to its community', got the highest mean of 3.60; while 'serves international cuisine dishes' got the lowest mean of 3.35. This implies that when it comes to cultural factors, the respondents favor destinations that preserve the culture, promote and produce exciting events, and welcome visitors from other cultures. Additionally, this further implies that the guests select a destination that embraces local traditions and customs.

These findings coincide with the findings of Durmaz (2014) who stated that the most important factor in consumer buying behavior in Turkey is the suitability of culture, beliefs, tradition, and customs of the goods and services that consumers will take.

Table 9 Cultural Factors Affecting the Guests' Buying Behavior

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. preserves cultural resources.	3.57	0.547	Strongly Agree
2. observes local custom and traditions.	3.57	0.536	Strongly Agree
3. serves international cuisine dishes.	3.35	0.633	Strongly Agree
4. promotes and produce exciting festival events.	3.59	0.585	Strongly Agree
5. accommodates guests from different countries.	3.56	0.554	Strongly Agree
6. makes creative design dedicated to its community.	3.60	0.553	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.54		Strongly Agree

Table 10 Social Factors Affecting the Guests' Buying Behavior

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. has modern features presented on destination's websites.	3.47	0.612	Strongly Agree
2. is highly recommended by family and friends	3.53	0.572	Strongly Agree
3. is an accredited establishment	3.55	0.560	Strongly Agree
4. is well-known excellent in service	3.59	0.555	Strongly Agree
5. employees are friendly and sociable	3.72	0.470	Strongly Agree
6. has known celebrities- visitors or guest	3.60	0.547	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.58		Strongly Agree

Table 10 shows the Social Factors Affecting the CvSU college students' Buying Behavior with an overall mean of 3.58 rated as Strongly Agree. Findings indicated that 'employees are friendly and sociable', got the highest mean of 3.72; while 'has modern features presented on destination's websites' got the lowest mean of 3.47. This implies that when it comes to social factors, the respondents favor tourism destinations that are well-known for their high standards of service as reflected by their accommodating staff, come highly recommended, and are accredited by governing bodies like the Department of Tourism. Additionally, this further implies that websites and social networking sites, including reviews, helpful vlogs, and blogs, and shared pictures of netizens and celebrities, continue to have a significant influence on visitors' decisions because travelers are searching for Instagramable sites and the latest trends.

Similar to the result of this study was that of Chaundhary (2018) who stated that the type of role played by a consumer in society and at home has a tremendous impact on buying behavior. According to a study by Makgosa (2010) on the vicarious role model influencing the purchase intention of teenagers show it is positively influenced especially the switching behavior. For instance, teens realize they are influenced directly or indirectly by their role models in their purchasing (Martin & Bush, 2000). After that Wyatt et al. (2008) share that the person who is insecure about their social status would likely purchase the product brands that expressed prestige to others and avoid from labeled as second-class. Tourism destinations visited by celebrities usually connote prestige luxury brands.

Table 11 shows the Personal Factors Affecting the CvSU college students' Buying Behavior with an overall mean of 3.52 rated as Strongly Agree. Findings indicated that 'offers affordable accommodations and services', got the highest mean of 3.61; while 'has an Intimate and luxurious environment' got the lowest mean of 3.45. This implies that when it comes to personal factors, the respondents favor tourism destinations that provide recreational and leisure activities at

budget-friendly rates. Moreover, this further implies that respondents prefer destinations where they will feel at ease, energized, and alive.

These findings conform to the study of Sahu & Pradhan (2017), who reported that the economic situation of the consumer has a significant influence on buying behavior. If the income and saving level of the consumer is high, then the consumer would buy a more expensive product compared to someone who has a lower income. It also mentioned that the choices in product and brand are influenced by economic circumstances such as spendable income, savings, assets, and debts.

Table 11 Personal Factors Affecting the Guests' Buying Behavior

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. caters services of different occasions	3.49	0.557	Strongly Agree
2. offers affordable accommodations and services.	3.61	0.556	Strongly Agree
3. has Intimate and luxurious environment.	3.45	0.571	Strongly Agree
4. provides events hall and other entertainment facilities.	3.53	0.556	Strongly Agree
5. has private rooms and facilities	3.56	0.537	Strongly Agree
6. has sports facilities, gym equipment and instructor.	3.47	0.607	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.52		Strongly Agree

Table 12 Psychological Factors Affecting the Guests' Buying Behavior

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. offers free stress and peace of mind.	3.66	0.517	Strongly Agree
2. has latest CCTV technology for its properties.	3.40	0.618	Strongly Agree
3. has security officers who are well trained.	3.48	0.626	Strongly Agree
4. has warm and comfortable rooms and beds.	3.65	0.541	Strongly Agree
5. with relaxing and pleasing atmosphere.	3.70	0.490	Strongly Agree
6. has recreational activities.	3.67	0.525	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.59		Strongly Agree

Table 12 shows the Psychological Factors Affecting the CvSU college students' Buying Behavior with an overall mean of 3.59 rated as Strongly Agree. Findings indicated that 'with relaxing and a pleasing atmosphere, got the highest mean of 3.70; while 'has latest CCTV technology for its properties 'got the lowest mean of 3.40. This implies that the respondents favor tourism destinations that can calm and relax them when it comes to psychological factors. This further implies that when choosing a tourism destination, visitors give careful consideration to the atmosphere, welcoming environment, safety, and security.

This finding was explained by Armstrong et al. (2011) who mentioned that motivation influences psychological factors. A motive comes from the individual need and want, where there is a presence of firm pressure to seek satisfaction and pleasure. Motivation pushes people to act and fulfill what they want up to their satisfaction level (Gunawan, 2015). A need becomes a motive and leads to a move.

Since the age of the respondents were categorized into 18 years old and below, 19 to 20, 21 to 22, and 23 years old and above, and the perceived brand equity was ordinal data, hence the Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine their significant difference at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the data analysis showed that the computed chi-squared value was 9.114 with its associated probability value of .028 less than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the age of the respondents and the perceived brand equity was

rejected. This means that the perceived brand equity was significantly affected by their age. This implies that as travelers' ages vary, so do their brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality of Cavite's tourism destinations.

This could be explained by the study conducted by Pinki (2014) that discussed age is considered as one of the important demographic variables that can have a deep influence on the purchase pattern of an individual. People of different age groups can show different buying patterns. Even age plays a role in choosing particular products or services keeping the other variables constant. Moreover, he concluded that his consumer buying pattern is not been the same throughout his life, his values, lifestyle, environment, hobbies, activities, and consumer habits have evolved throughout his life.

3.4. Difference in the perceived brand equity when grouped according to the demographic profile

Table 13 CvSU College Students' perceived Brand Equity when grouped according to Age

Age	Mean Rank	Chi Square Computed	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
18 yrs old and below	215.89	9.114	0.028	significant	Reject
19 to 20 years old	158.05				
21 to 22 years old	172.23				
23 yrs old and above	204.95				

Table 14 Post Hoc Test for CvSU College Students' perceived Brand Equity when grouped according to Age

Sample 1- Sample 2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
19 to 20 years old-21 to 22 years old	-14.185	11.403	-1.244	0.213
19 to 20 years old-23 years old and above	-46.900	20.047	-2.339	0.019
19 to 20 years old-18 years old and below	57.846	27.281	2.120	0.034
21 to 22 years old-23 years old and above	-32.715	20.318	-1.610	0.107
21 to 22 years old-18 years old and below	43.661	27.480	1.589	0.112

A post hoc test was used to determine which among the groups differ significantly at a 0.05 level of significance. Results revealed that 19 to 20 year olds were found to have p-values less than the specified 0.05 level of significance. This means that students from 19 to 20 years old have the largest difference in their perceived brand equity.

Table 15 CvSU College Students' perceived Brand Equity when grouped according to Sex

Sex	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Male	152.26	6930.500	0.138	not significant	Accept
Female	173.51				

The Mann-Whitney U Test was used to determine the significant difference between sex and the perceived brand equity of CvSU College students using a 0.05 level of significance.

Results of the study show that sex was found to have p-values more than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the sex of the respondents and the perceived brand equity of CvSU College students was accepted. This means that the perceived brand equity was not significantly affected by their sex. This further implies that choosing a tourism destination does not take into account one's sexual preferences. The degree to which brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality are shared equally by men and women.

This is contrary to Ries and Ries (2004) who observed that gender appears to influence brand equity. males are loyal based on product performance and females only if service performance is acceptable (Moutinho and Goode, 1995).

Table 16 CvSU College Students' perceived Brand Equity when grouped according to Place of Residence

Place of Residence	Mean Rank	Chi Square Computed	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Alfonso	212.96	29.019	0.144	not significant	Accept
Amadeo	118.58				
Bacoor City	146.75				
Carmona	135.00				
Cavite City	64.38				
Dasmariñas City	145.28				
General Emilio Aguinaldo	243.00				
General Mariano Alvarez	193.10				
General Trias City	169.42				
Imus City	149.17				
Indang	186.90				
Kawit	241.50				
Magallanes	149.33				
Maragondon	328.50				
Mendez	233.75				
Naic	167.87				
Noveleta	120.00				
Rosario	237.50				
Silang	188.55				
Tagaytay City	145.63				
Tanza	189.89				
Ternate	291.50				
Trece Martires City	163.73				

The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine the significant difference between the place of residence and the perceived brand equity of CvSU College students using a 0.05 level of significance.

As shown in Table 17, the computed chi-squared value was 29.019 with its associated probability value of .144 more than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the place of residence of the respondents and the perceived brand equity of CvSU College students was accepted. This means that the perceived brand equity was not significantly affected by their place of residence. This further implies that a consumer's home address has little bearing on how they perceive a tourism destination's quality, brand loyalty, brand awareness, and brand associations.

The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine the significant difference between the monthly family income and the perceived brand equity of CvSU College students using a 0.05 level of significance.

As shown in Table 18, the computed chi-squared value was 1.702 with its associated probability value of .636 more than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the monthly family

income of the respondents and the perceived brand equity of CvSU College students was accepted. This means that their monthly family income did not significantly affect the perceived brand equity. This further implies that their perceived quality, brand loyalty, brand awareness, and brand associations are not influenced by their economic status.

Table 17 CvSU College Students’ perceived Brand Equity when grouped according to Monthly Family Income

Monthly Family Income	Mean Rank	Chi Square Computed	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Less than Php 10,000	175.03	1.702	0.636	not significant	Accept
Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	171.75				
Php 20,001 to Php 30,000	165.68				
Php 30,001 and above	148.44				

3.5. Difference in the CvSU college students ’buying behavior when grouped according to their demographic profile

Table 18 CvSU College Students’ Buying Behaviour when grouped according to Age

Age	Mean Rank	Chi Square Computed	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
18 yrs old and below	193.75	1.574	0.665	not significant	Accept
19 to 20 years old	171.42				
21 to 22 years old	164.10				
23 yrs old and above	178.63				

Since the age of the respondents were categorized into 18 years old and below, 19 to 20, 21 to 22, and 23 years old and above, and the buying behavior was ordinal data, hence the Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine their significant difference at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the data analysis showed that the computed chi-squared value was 1.574 with its associated probability value of .665 more than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the age of the respondents and the buying behavior was accepted. This means that their buying behavior was not significantly affected by their age. This further implies that travelers of all ages took the same factors when visiting Cavite’s tourism destinations.

The result is contrary to Bansal et. al (2015) who claimed that age influences the purchase decision. The elder generation, adults, and teenagers have complete autonomy to make their own purchasing decisions. As people grow, their needs change. Similar changes appear in their buying decision-making patterns.

Table 19 CvSU College Students’ Buying Behavior when grouped according to Sex

Sex	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Male	141.00	6300.000	0.015	significant	Reject
Female	175.74				

The Mann-Whitney U Test was used to determine the significant difference between sex and the buying behavior of CvSU College students using a 0.05 level of significance.

Results of the study show that sex was found to have p-values less than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the sex of the respondents and the buying behavior of CvSU College students was rejected. This means that their buying behavior was significantly affected by their sex. This further implies that choosing a tourism destination to visit takes into account sexual preferences. When choosing a destination, men and women have different cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors to consider.

This result could be explained by Djumrianti and Oseso-Asare (2021) who claimed that women arrange the family income. The purchasing of family holiday packages was dependent on them, including managing holiday budgets, seeking information, and arranging travel documents.

Table 20 CvSU College Students' Buying Behavior when grouped according to Place of Residence

Place of Residence	Mean Rank	Chi Square Computed	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Alfonso	221.88	29.465	0.132	not significant	Accept
Amadeo	235.08				
Bacoor City	140.05				
Carmona	141.17				
Cavite City	79.75				
Dasmariñas City	163.18				
General Emilio Aguinaldo	283.00				
General Mariano Alvarez	233.55				
General Trias City	158.65				
Imus City	136.47				
Indang	166.56				
Kawit	247.25				
Magallanes	124.17				
Maragondon	283.00				
Mendez	181.92				
Naic	176.29				
Noveleta	126.00				
Rosario	215.00				
Silang	199.41				
Tagaytay City	156.44				
Tanza	195.63				
Ternate	242.75				
Trece Martires City	153.12				

The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine the significant difference between the place of residence and the buying behavior of CvSU College students using a 0.05 level of significance.

As shown in Table 20, the computed chi-squared value was 29.465 with its associated probability value of .132 more than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the place of residence of the respondents and the buying behavior of CvSU College students was accepted. This means that the buying behavior was not significantly affected by their place of residence. This further implies that a consumer's home address is irrelevant when deciding which tourism destination to visit.

Table 21 CvSU College Students' Buying Behavior when grouped according to Monthly Family Income

Monthly Family Income	Mean Rank	Chi Square Computed	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Less than Php 10,000	173.09	1.881	0.598	not significant	Accept
Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	166.98				
Php 20,001 to Php 30,000	178.04				
Php 30,001 and above	148.70				

The Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine the significant difference between the monthly family income and the buying behavior of CvSU College students using a 0.05 level of significance.

As shown in Table 21, the computed chi-squared value was 1.881 with its associated probability value of .598 more than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the monthly family income of the respondents and the buying behavior of CvSU College students was accepted. This means that their buying behavior was not significantly affected by their monthly family income. This further implies that their money does not affect their decision-making process when selecting a tourism destination to visit.

This is contrary to the study conducted by Pratap (2017) which stated that across different income levels, the difference in product choices and buying patterns can easily be marked. People with higher disposable income spend more on vacations and tours.

3.6. Relationship between perceived brand equity and the buying behavior of CvSU college students

Table 22 CvSU College Students' Perceived Brand Equity and Buying Behavior

Variables	r_s value	P-value	Interpretation	Decision to Ho
Brand Equity * Buying Behavior	.658	<.001	There is a moderate significant positive relationship	Reject

Coefficient Range	Strength of Association
± 0.91 to ± 1.00	Very Strong
± 0.71 to ± 0.90	High
± 0.41 to ± 0.70	Moderate
± 0.21 to ± 0.40	Small but definite relationship
± 0.00 to ± 0.20	Slight, almost negligible

Source: Hair, J., Money, A., Samuel, P., & Page, M. (2007).

3.7. Correlation Coefficient

Spearman's rank-order correlation was run to determine the relationship between CvSU College students' perceived brand equity and buying behavior using a 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study show that the respondents' perceived brand equity and buying behavior were found to have p-values less than the specified 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the variables was rejected. There was a moderate, positive correlation between CvSU College students' perceived brand equity and buying behavior, which was statistically significant ($r_s = .658$, $p = .001$). This means that their buying behavior was significantly affected by their perceived brand equity. This further shows that when choosing a tourism destination to visit, participants consider brand equity and buying behavior.

This can be explained by the study conducted by Satvati et. al. (2016) that talked about brand equity as associated with some aspects of consumer behavior including willingness to pay extra costs, brand preference, and purchase intention.

A strong brand creates added value for products that leads to customer preference in selection. In the later stages of purchase behavior, brand preference may lead to more payment and purchase intention by the consumer.

4. Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that:

The majority of the guests visiting the tourism destinations in Cavite are female, young, with a family earning above minimum wage in a month, and living in the urban areas of Cavite.

Perceived quality came out to be the most dominant factor considered by CvSU college students in visiting tourist destinations. It was shown that repeat purchases are more likely to be made by travelers who are emotionally connected to and attached to a brand. This can only occur when a user and a brand have a close, long-lasting relationship.

Psychological factors prevail to be the most important factor the CvSU college students considered. When making purchases and making a judgment of the brand that influenced their choice to make the buy, consumers have specific attitudes and beliefs. Consumer attitudes toward ecologically friendly travel destinations are influencing their choices of destinations for sustainable tourism.

CvSU College students' demographic profile in terms of sex, place of residence, and monthly family income did not affect their perceived brand equity. Only age profile has a significant difference with perceived brand equity. Teenagers, young people, and adults all have various values, lifestyles, environments, pastimes, and habits that have an impact on how they perceive brand loyalty, awareness, associations, and perceived quality.

CvSU College students' demographic profile in terms of age, place of residence, and monthly family income did not affect their buying behavior. Only sex has a significant difference with consumer buying behavior. Female tends to be the crucial decision-makers concerning family holidays since they manage the family's finances. They were responsible for handling holiday expenditures, researching, setting up travel paperwork, and choosing family vacation packages.

CvSU College students' buying behavior in terms of cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors is affected by their perceived brand equity in terms of brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand associations, and perceived quality. Therefore, this could conclude that Tourism Destinations in Cavite with higher brand equity levels would generate higher customer visits. Also, consumer buying behavior was associated with more willingness to visit a destination.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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